

Preferential Solvation of Copper(II) Salts in Water—Dimethylformamide Mixtures

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Preferential solvation of copper(II) salts, viz. copper(II) iodate, benzoate and formate, has been studied in the binary mixtures of *N,N*-dimethylformamide (DMF) and water at 30° by solubility and emf measurements. The Gibbs transfer energies of these salts (from water to water-DMF mixtures) were calculated from solubilities and found to increase up to $X_{\text{DMF}} = 0.3$ and decrease thereafter for copper(II) benzoate and formate whereas $\Delta G_{\text{t}}^{\circ}$ of copper(II) iodate increases with the addition of DMF. The transfer free energy of Cu^{2+} ion is negative and decreases continuously whereas that of anions is positive and increases with the addition of DMF. The solvent transport numbers were found to be positive for all the salts and pass through a maximum of $\Delta_{\text{max}} = 0.88$ at $X_{\text{DMF}} = 0.15$, $\Delta_{\text{max}} = 2.11$ at $X_{\text{DMF}} = 0.45$ and $\Delta_{\text{max}} = 2.04$ at $X_{\text{DMF}} = 0.55$ for copper(II) iodate, benzoate and formate respectively. The results indicate a heteroselective solvation of these salts, i.e. Cu^{2+} ion being selectively solvated by DMF and the anions by water.

Many physicochemical phenomena like solubilities of electrolytes rates of chemical reactions, phase separation processes, and redox potentials are strongly influenced by the selective solvation of ions in mixed solvents^{1,2}. Some technological applications, based on this principle, such as electrodeposition³, metal refining⁴, and in high energy density batteries^{5,6}, have been suggested. The present status in this field has been recently reviewed⁷. In earlier studies from our laboratory, the preferential solvation of Ag^+ , Cu^{2+} , and Zn^{2+} salts in binary solvent mixtures containing DMSO^{8,9}, AN^{10,11}, DMF^{12,13} and pyridine^{14,15} employing the Gibbs energies of transfer and solvent transport number (Δ) measurements has been reported. In continuation of the above, the present work deals with the selective solvation behaviour of few copper(II) salts, viz. copper(II) benzoate, copper(II) formate and copper(II) iodate in water-DMF mixtures. Such investigations involving multivalent unsymmetrical electrolytes have been scarcely reported in literature.

Results and Discussion

The thermodynamic solubility product (K_{sp}) is related to the solubilities of the copper salts as

$$K_{\text{sp}} = 4s^3\gamma_{\pm}^3 \quad (1)$$

where γ_{\pm} is the mean molal activity coefficient of the salt and it was calculated from the extended Debye-Hückel limiting relation using the dielectric constant data of the solvent mixtures reported earlier¹⁶. The ion-size parameter $\alpha = 12.0$ Å for copper(II) benzoate, $\alpha = 10.5$ Å for copper(II) iodate and $\alpha = 9.5$ Å for copper(II) formate¹⁷ were used in these calculations. The solubility (s) and solubility product (K_{sp}) of these salts in water-DMF mixtures are given in Table 1.

TABLE 1—SOLUBILITY (s) AND SOLUBILITY PRODUCT (K_{sp}) OF COPPER(II) IODATE, BENZOATE AND FORMATE IN WATER-DMF MIXTURES AT 30°

X_{DMF}	D^*	$\text{Cu}(\text{IO}_3)_2$		$\text{Cu}(\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{COO})_2$		$\text{Cu}(\text{HCOO})_2$	
		$10^5 s^{**}$	(pK_{sp})	$10^3 s^{**}$	pK_{sp}	$10s^{**}$	(pK_{sp})
0.0	76.7	311.18	7.14	7.80	6.02	7.36	0.609
0.1	73.1	34.91	9.87	10.60	5.67	1.13	2.91
0.2	64.6	19.26	10.6	3.15	7.18	1.11	3.03
0.3	58.7	5.50	12.2	2.34	7.57	0.93	3.34
0.4	52.8	3.47	12.8	2.72	7.44	—	—
0.5	48.6	0.92	14.5	4.44	6.90	2.34	2.48
0.6	45.4	0.55	15.2	6.25	6.55	7.13	1.26
0.7	42.6	0.42	15.6	8.58	6.24	8.15	1.21
0.8	40.3	0.38	15.7	14.20	5.73	8.89	1.19
0.9	38.1	0.33	15.7	16.70	5.61	9.98	1.16
1.0	36.5	0.18	16.6	17.90	5.58	8.36	1.45

* Taken from Ref. 16. ** Solubility in mol kg⁻¹; accuracy $\pm 0.5\%$.

The Gibbs energies of transfer of the salts, ΔG_t^0 (salt) from water to water-DMF mixtures were calculated from the equation,

$$\Delta G_t^0(\text{salt}) = -RT \ln \frac{K_{sp}(S)}{K_{sp}(R)} \quad (2)$$

where S is the solvent mixtures (water-DMF) and R is the reference solvent (water).

The Gibbs transfer energy of the copper(II) ion, $\Delta G_t^0(\text{Cu}^{2+})$, is related to ΔG_t^0 of the salt and anion by the equation,

$$\Delta G_t^0(\text{CuX}_2) = \Delta G_t^0(\text{Cu}^{2+}) + 2\Delta G_t^0(\text{X}^-)$$

where, $\text{X} = \text{IO}_3^-$, HCOO^- and $\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{COO}^-$. The transfer energies of the anion as calculated above are given in Table 2. The variation of ΔG_t^0 of the salts and the ions with compositions are shown in Fig. 1.

TABLE 2 - GIBBS TRANSFER ENERGY OF COPPER(II) SALTS AND IONS IN WATER-DMF MIXTURES AT 30°

X_{DMF}	$\Delta G_t^0(\text{kJ mol}^{-1})$						
	$\text{Cu}(\text{IO}_3)_2$	$\text{Cu}(\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{COO})_2$	$\text{Cu}(\text{HCOO})_2$	Cu^{2+} **	IO_3^-	$\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{COO}^-$	HCOO^-
0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0
0.1	15.8	-2.0	13.4	-1.7	8.8	-0.15	7.6
0.2	20.3	6.7	14.1	-3.3	11.8	5.0	8.7
0.3	29.5	8.0	15.8	-4.9	17.2	6.5	10.4
0.4	33.0	8.3		-6.9	20.0	7.6	—
0.5	42.9	5.2	10.9	-8.6	25.8	6.9	9.8
0.6	46.8	3.1	3.8	-10.3	28.6	6.7	7.1
0.7	48.9	1.3	3.5	-12.0	30.6	6.7	7.8
0.8	49.6	-1.7	3.4	-13.8	31.7	6.1	8.6
0.9	50.6	-2.4	3.2	-15.8	33.2	6.7	9.5
1.0	55.0	-2.6	4.9	-17.9	36.5	7.7	11.4

* Accurate to ± 0.2 unit, ** Taken from Ref. 31 at 25°.

It is seen from Table 1 that solubilities of copper(II) benzoate and copper(II) formate initially pass through a minimum at $X_{\text{DMF}} = 0.3$ and then continuously increase with the addition of DMF. The solubility of copper(II) iodate, on the other hand, decreases continuously with the addition of DMF. The Gibbs transfer energies calculated from equation (2) for copper(II) benzoate and copper(II) formate increase up to $X_{\text{DMF}} = 0.3$ and decrease thereafter whereas ΔG_t^0 of copper(II) iodate increases with the addition of DMF. The transfer energy of the cation, $\Delta G_t^0(\text{Cu}^{2+})$ is negative and decreases continuously

Fig. 1. Variation of ΔG_t^0 for copper(II) salts and constituent ions in water-DMF mixtures at 30°: (o) $\text{Cu}(\text{IO}_3)_2$, (Δ) $\text{Cu}(\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{COO})_2$, (c) $\text{Cu}(\text{HCOO})_2$, (●) Cu^{2+} , (\blacktriangle) IO_3^- (●) $\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{COO}^-$ and (◊) HCOO^- .

with the addition of DMF, indicating that the transfer of Cu^{2+} ion from water to water-DMF mixtures is thermodynamically favoured. Thus it may be concluded that copper(II) ion is preferentially solvated by DMF which can be explained on the basis of Lewis acid-base interaction between copper(II) ion and DMF. In fact a complex of the type $[\text{Cu}(\text{DMF})_6]^{2+}$ between copper(II) ion and DMF has been reported¹⁸. On the other hand, the Gibbs transfer energies of the anions, viz. benzoate, iodate and formate are positive and increase with the addition of DMF. It may be noted that the transfer energies of benzoate and formate are nearly constant beyond $X_{\text{DMF}} = 0.5$. Also the slope of the plot ΔG_t^0 (anion), viz. X_{DMF} increases significantly in the region $X_{\text{DMF}} = 0.1$ to 0.5. The results indicate that these ions are preferentially hydrated by water up to $X_{\text{DMF}} = 0.5$ and thereafter the solvation shell composition around the ions in the primary zone appears to be unchanged. The small changes in ΔG_t^0 observed beyond this composition is due to the perturbation of the secondary solvation shell due to the entry of DMF. The slightly less positive values of the transfer free energy of the benzoate ion in comparison to formate ion may be attributed to the $-I$ effect

(electron-withdrawing) of the phenyl group. The anion-water interactions are mainly governed by the hydrogen bond formation between the anion and water molecules. Thus a heteroselective solvation of the salts in these mixtures is inferred.

A comparison of the free energies of transfer of copper(II) ion and anions such as benzoate and iodate from water to DMF, DMSO and pyridine is given in Table 3.

TABLE 3 – COMPARISON OF FREE ENERGIES OF TRANSFER (kJ mol^{-1}) OF COPPER(II) ION AND ANIONS VIZ. BENZOATE AND IODATE WATER TO OTHER SOLVENTS AT 30°

Solvent	Donor no. (D_N) [*]	$\Delta G_T^\circ(\text{Cu}^{2+})$	$\Delta G_T^\circ(\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{COO}^-)$	$\Delta G_T^\circ(\text{IO}_3^-)$
DMF ^a	26.6	-17.9	7.7	36.5
DMSO ^b	29.8	-56.7	25.2	24.2
Py ^b	33.1	-77.5	34.7	55.2

*Ref. 20. ^aPresent study. ^bRef. 21.

It is interesting to point out that as the donor number of the solvent, which reflects the behaviour of these solvents towards borderline cations¹⁹ such as Cu^{2+} , increases, the free energy of transfer becomes more negative, i.e. the donor strength towards Cu^{2+} ion increases, which is in the order, $\text{DMF} < \text{DMSO} < \text{Py}$. The reverse is generally true for anions where water acts as a hard acid towards the anions such as $\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{COO}^-$ and IO_3^- .

Solvent transport number : The solvent transport number (Δ) of DMF in these mixtures for the various salts was evaluated from the emf data of cell (A) using the relation,

$$\Delta_{\text{DMF}} = \frac{FE}{RT} \cdot \frac{(X_{\text{DMF}}(1-X_{\text{DMF}}))}{(X_{\text{DMF}}''-X_{\text{DMF}}')} \cdot \left(1 + \frac{d \ln f_{\text{DMF}}}{d \ln X_{\text{DMF}}} \right)$$

where the various terms have their usual significance²². The activity coefficient term accounts for the deviation of the solvent mixtures from ideal behaviour and is taken to be zero for water-DMF mixtures on the basis of the vapour pressure data of Geller²³. The emf of the cell (A) and the calculated Δ_{DMF} values are given in Table 4.

TABLE 4— EMF DATA AND SOLVENT TRANSPORT NUMBER (Δ) OF DMF FOR COPPER(II) SALTS IN WATER-DMF MIXTURES AT 30°

X_{DMF}	$\text{Cu}(\text{IO}_3)_2$		$\text{Cu}(\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{COO})_2$		$\text{Cu}(\text{HCOO})_2$	
	-E(mV)	Δ	-E(mV)	Δ	-E(mV)	Δ
0.05	14.5±1.0	0.27±0.01	12.5±0.5	0.23±0.01	14.5±0.5	0.27±0.0
0.15	18.0±1.0	0.88±0.05	18.0±1.0	0.88±0.05	16.2±1.0	0.81±0.03
0.25	8.3±0.5	0.60±0.03	21.3±1.0	1.53±0.07	18.0±1.0	1.30±0.06
0.35	7.0±0.5	0.61±0.04	23.4±0.5	2.04±0.04	20.0±0.5	1.74±0.05
0.45	7.8±1.0	0.74±0.05	22.2±0.5	2.11±0.04	21.0±0.5	1.99±0.05
0.55	6.8±0.5	0.64±0.05	18.1±1.0	1.72±0.09	21.5±0.5	2.04±0.04
0.65	7.3±0.5	0.64±0.04	17.1±0.5	1.45±0.08	22.2±1.0	1.96±0.06
0.75	8.0±0.5	0.58±0.03	15.2±0.5	1.09±0.04	20.5±0.5	1.47±0.04
0.85	9.6±0.5	0.47±0.02	12.5±0.5	0.61±0.03	19.0±0.5	0.93±0.01
0.95	10.9±1.0	0.20±0.01	23.5±1.0	0.43±0.01	22.0±0.5	0.40±0.01

The variation of Δ_{DMF} with X_{DMF} is shown in Fig. 2. It is seen that the Δ_{DMF} values for all

Fig. 2. Variation of Δ with X_{DMF} in water-DMF mixtures at 30° : copper (II), (Δ) iodate, (\circ) benzoate and (\circ) formate.

the salts are positive and pass through a maximum of $\Delta_{\text{DMF}} = 0.9$ at $X_{\text{DMF}} = 0.1$ for copper(II) iodate, $\Delta_{\text{DMF}} = 2.1$ at $X_{\text{DMF}} = 0.45$ for copper(II) benzoate and $\Delta_{\text{DMF}} = 2.0$ at $X_{\text{DMF}} = 0.55$ for copper(II) formate. The Δ_{DMF} values for copper(II) iodate are found to be significantly less than the case of other salts presumably because of the fairly low solubilities of the salt. These results indicate that there is an enrichment of 0.9, 2.1 and 2.0 moles

of DMF, respectively, per Faraday relative to the mean molar velocity of the solvent mixtures as reference²⁴ in the cathode compartment when solutions of the salts are electrolysed in water-DMF mixtures at the given compositions. Δ_{DMF} is given by

$$\Delta_{DMF} = (X_w n_{DMF}^+ - X_{DMF} n_w^+) \frac{t^+}{2} - (X_w n_{DMF}^- - X_{DMF} n_w^-) t^-$$

where n and t represent the solvation number and the transport number of both the ions in these mixtures. For heteroselectively solvated salts, n_{DMF}^+ and n_w^- are large while n_{DMF}^- and n_w^+ are small resulting in large positive Δ_{DMF} values as observed in these mixtures. The transport of DMF into the cathode compartment occurs mainly through copper(II) ion while the anions transport water in the opposite direction. The large Δ_{DMF} value arises due to the additive nature of the above two effects. Thus a heteroselective solvation of the salts in these mixtures is indicated which provides support to the conclusions arrived from transfer free energy data.

Experimental

N,N-Dimethylformamide (DMF) (Merck, G.R.) after a preliminary vacuum distillation, was dried over anhydrous copper sulphate for a week and again distilled under vacuum following the procedure of Faulkner and Bard²⁵. The fraction boiling at 45° under 15 mm/Hg pressure was collected and stored out of contact with air. It had a density, $d^{25} = 0.9440 \text{ g cm}^{-3}$ which is in good agreement with literature value ($d^{25} = 0.9442$)²³.

Double-distilled conductivity water was used in the preparation of solvent mixtures. Copper(II) benzoate was prepared according to the procedure reported earlier²⁶. The salt was first dried in air and then successively over anhydrous CaCl_2 and P_2O_5 at 110–20° under reduced pressure for over 2 days to yield the anhydrous compound. Copper(II) iodate was prepared by double-decomposition of copper(II) nitrate and potassium iodate in aqueous solution²⁷ and the purified salt was heated to 240° to yield the anhydrous salt. Copper(II) formate was prepared by exact neutralisation of basic copper(II) carbonate with formic acid²⁸. The salt thus formed

was recrystallised from conductivity water, dried and the anhydrous salt was obtained by heating up to 100°. The purity of the salts was checked by estimation of their copper content by spectrophotometry.

The copper electrodes were prepared by electrolytically depositing copper on to platinum spiral electrodes (0.5 mm)²⁹. The electrodes whose bias potentials were less than 0.5 mV, were used in all the emf measurements. A Keithley 602 solid state electrometer having an input impedance greater than $10^{14} \Omega$ was used in all the measurements. All measurements were carried out at $30 \pm 0.1^\circ$.

Methods :

Solubility measurements : Saturated solution of the salts were prepared as described earlier³⁰. The solubilities were determined by estimating the copper content by inductively coupled plasma-atomic emission spectrometry (ICP-AES, ARL-3410 with mini-torch) at a wavelength of 324.754 nm and at least two independent determinations were made in each solvent composition. The agreement between them was better than $\pm 0.2\%$.

Determination of $\Delta G_i^\circ (\text{Cu}^{2+})$: The standard Gibbs transfer energies of Cu^{2+} ion, $\Delta G_i^\circ (\text{Cu}^{2+})$, from water to water-DMF mixtures, determined on the basis of the negligible liquid junction potential (nLJP) method by Lewandowski³¹, were used in calculating transfer energies of the anions.

Determination of solvent transport number (Δ) : The solvent transport number (Δ_{DMF}) for the various salts was determined over the complete range of solvent compositions by employing a concentration cell (A) with transference of the type,

where, $X = \text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{COO}^-$, HCOO^- and IO_3^- as suggested by Wagner³², in which the two half-cells contained saturated solutions of the salts in solvent mixtures differing in composition by 0.1 mole fractions.

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